

Statistical approaches enabling technology-specific assay interference prediction from large screening data sets

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ABSTRACT

High throughput screening (HTS) technologies allow the biological testing of hundreds of thousands of compounds per day. Typically, a substantial proportion of the initial hits obtained by HTS are artifacts caused by assay interference. Therefore, global and technology-specific *in silico* models for identifying and predicting compounds interfering with biological assays have been developed. The global models benefit from training on large screening data sets, while the specialized models benefit from training on assay technology-specific experimental data. In this work, we develop and explore strategies for generating better predictors of technology-specific assay interference by utilizing the large bioactivity data matrices global models are trained on and employing partially new compound labeling approaches to maintain the assay technology awareness of specialized models. We demonstrate the utility of the statistically derived interference labels in machine learning using fluorescence-based assay interference as a representative example. Our random forest and multi-layer perceptron classifiers showed improved performance compared to existing models, achieving Matthews correlation coefficients (MCCs) of up to 0.47 on holdout data and up to 0.45 on an external test set. These results demonstrate that accurate assay-specific interference labels can be derived from large bioactivity data matrices, enabling the development of new machine-learning models without the need for further experimental data.

Introduction

Modern biological assay technologies, automation, and robotics enable the high-throughput screening (HTS) of hundreds of thousands of compounds a day. However, only a fraction of the hits identified with these technologies represent genuine, specific target modulators, while many are the result of assay interference triggered by the compounds [1, 2]. The most common cause of interference across the different assay platforms and technologies is the formation of colloidal aggregates by the test compounds [3]. Among the most relevant types of technology-related interference are autofluorescence (that is, the emission of a fluorescence signal by the compound) and chemical quenching (that is, the reduction of a fluorescence signal by excited state reactions or energy transfer) [4].

Today, HTS facilities have elaborate experimental protocols and techniques in place that are designed to prevent and detect assay interference [1]. These include (i) the screening with non-ionic detergents to prevent compound aggregation [5], (ii) the use of novel fluorophores emitting in a different region of the electromagnetic spectrum (e.g., red light) to reduce spurious signals associated with intrinsic compound fluorescence [6], (iii) the use of orthogonal assays to confirm primary hits, and, (iv) the implementation of counter-screen assays to identify interfering compounds [7]. However, these experimental procedures are resource-demanding and not universally available. Hence, efforts to develop *in silico* models for predicting compounds likely to cause interference in biological assays have increased in recent years [8].

Machine learning models are now taking the lead in assay

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interference prediction. They can be categorized into global models and specialized models. Global models are typically trained on large data sets in which hundreds of thousands of compounds are tested against (in total) hundreds to thousands of biological assays. From this bioactivity matrix, the models learn which molecular features make compounds “frequent hitters”.

Frequent hitters are compounds showing unexpectedly high hit rates across biological assays. Substantially higher hit rates are often indicative of assay interference (note that a minority of frequent hitters are true promiscuous compounds that interact specifically, reversibly, with multiple, distinct biomacromolecules) [9]. One example of a global model for frequent hitter prediction is HitDexter [10]. HitDexter is trained on a large bioactivity matrix compiled from PubChem BioAssay [11]. For training, compounds were assigned positive “promiscuity” labels if the active-to-tested ratio (ATR; that is, the ratio between the number of assays that reported a compound as active and the total number of assays in which a compound was tested) was above a specified threshold (typically, one to three standard deviations above the average across all compounds). Otherwise, they are assigned negative labels.

The global models for assay interference prediction benefit from the large screening data sets available for training from sources such as PubChem BioAssay. However, they are agnostic of assay technologies, setups, and protocols. This is a considerable limitation because many types of assay interference only occur under specific conditions. For example, compounds causing assay interference in fluorescence-based assays because of their autofluorescence behavior may show benign behavior in other types of assays.

Specialized machine-learning models have been developed for specific assay technologies. They are trained on individual counter-screen and orthogonal assay data sets, typically smaller than the training sets used by the global models. The reported approaches include models for autofluorescence prediction, such as those of David et al. [12], InterPred [13], and ChemFLuo [14], and models for luciferase inhibition prediction, such as Luciferase Advisor [15] and ChemFluc [16]. Several validation studies concluded that the performance and applicability of the specialized models are limited and suggest that the quantity of measured data available for the training of this type of model is likely the bottleneck [12,14,16].

In this work, we develop a statistical approach that enables the development of assay technology-specific predictors of assay interference from large screening data sets, thus leveraging the advantages of global and specialized models. More specifically, the approach compares the hit rates obtained for compounds with a specific assay technology to those obtained with assays based on other technologies. Thus, compounds behaving distinctly with a specific assay technology can be identified.

For assigning bioactivity labels, three statistical methods are explored: the established ATR, a noise-to-active ratio (NAR) that considers both the background signal and bioactivity readout of HTS assays, and Fisher’s exact test. To our knowledge, this is the first study in which assay-specific interference is addressed without using counter-screen data to label interfering compounds. We exemplify and validate the suitability of this approach by generating machine-learning models for predicting the interference of small molecules in fluorescence-based assays. The evaluation of the machine learning models with an external test set of autofluorescent and non-autofluorescent compounds confirms the effectiveness of the proposed labeling approach. Moreover, the performance achieved by our models indicates that augmented data sets can yield better models for the prediction of compounds interfering with fluorescence-based assays.

Methods

Data sets

Measured bioactivity data were extracted from the pool of historical single-dose HTS data available at Bayer AG, employing the following three criteria for assay and compound selection:

1. Assays must be designed to probe the interaction of a compound with a specific protein or pathway
2. Assays must have bioactivity recorded for at least 80 % of the compounds in the dataset
3. Compounds must have bioactivity recorded for at least 80 % of the assays.

In this framework, the bioactivity readouts from the HTS assay are already preprocessed and normalized [17], and reported as z-score values. For compounds measured multiple times in the same assay, averaged z-score values were used.

The resulting bioactivity data set (hereafter referred to as “Bayer AG data set”) comprises 1,488,407 compounds measured in a total of 99 biochemical and 88 cell-based assays using different fluorescent dyes (56, 23, and 8 assays using blue, green, and red fluorescent dyes, respectively), FRET or TR-FRET technologies (14 and 10 assays, respectively), and bioluminescence detection systems (76 assays). For all compounds, non-isomeric canonical SMILES were generated with RDKit [18]. As part of this process, minor (i.e., salt) components were removed with the ChEMBL Structure Pipeline [19]. This processing sometimes led to multiple instances (molecules) with identical canonical SMILES representations but inconsistent bioactivity readouts. These inconsistencies were removed to avoid conflicting bioactivity data. The processed data set holds 1,441,034 compounds, with 296,830,391 readouts recorded with a total of 187 different assays.

In preparation for model development, the data set was partitioned into a “training set”, a “validation set”, and a “test set” using a molecular scaffold split strategy. This procedure included (i) the generation of Morgan fingerprints (radius 2; length 2048 bits) for all compounds (with RDKit), (ii) the generation of Murcko scaffolds (with RDKit), (iii) the grouping of molecules sharing the same scaffold and (iv) the random assignment of groups of molecules sharing the same scaffold to the training set (80 % of the data), validation set (10 %), or test set (10 %). The use of a scaffold split strategy aimed to exclude trivial examples from the validation and test sets, thus providing a test set for evaluating the models’ generalization power.

Following the work of Yang et al. [14], an external test set was compiled from PubChem Bioassay AID 1696 and AID 720678. AID 1696 is a fluorescence-based counter-screen assay for detecting fluorescence artifacts in HTS assays for inhibitors of the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* cell wall enzymes RmlC (AID 1532) and RmlD (AID 1533). AID 720678 is a cell-based HTS assay designed to identify compounds that exhibit autofluorescence at a wavelength of 460 nm. The compounds were preprocessed using the same protocol described for the Bayer AG data set. The remaining 10,691 compounds were then compared to all compounds present in the training set, and any test compound with a maximum Tanimoto Coefficient (TC) of 1.0 was removed from the test set. The final external test set consisted of 10,031 unique structures.

A set of known aggregators [20] served as a further test set for the models. After preprocessing with the identical protocol described above, the set consisted of 12,643 known aggregators. None of these aggregators is present in the Bayer AG training set.

The preprocessed set of known aggregators was complemented with an equal number of compounds randomly selected from the ChEMBL database [21] to represent the negative class (i.e., putative non-aggregators). Only compounds structurally distinct from those in the Bayer AG training set were considered.

Compound labeling

The readouts of all 187 assays were converted via z-scores into binary activity labels applying $|z\text{-score}| \geq 4$ as the threshold (in a standard normal distribution or z-distribution, a z-score exceeding 4 corresponds to a p-value $\ll 0.01$, providing statistical significance about the observations). In addition, for the 56 assays based on blue fluorescence, the measured background emission signals (i.e., emission signals at time zero) were converted into binary “noise labels” applying $|z\text{-score}|$ thresholds of 1.0.

From the binarized assay readouts, binary labels describing the capacity of a compound to interfere with assays based on blue fluorescence were derived utilizing (i) active-to-tested ratios (ATRs), (ii) Fisher’s exact test, and (iii) ratios calculated for the background noise and the bioactivity signal (noise-to-active ratios, or NARs).

The ATR-based approach puts two ATR values into perspective: the ATR calculated from the outcomes of all assays based on blue fluorescence (ATR_{Fluo}) and the ATR based on the outcomes of all non-fluorescence-based assays (ATR_{Other}). Positive assay interference labels were assigned to any compounds for which:

$$ATR_{Fluo} \geq E[ATR_{Other}] + t \cdot \sigma(ATR_{Other}) \quad (1)$$

where $E[ATR_{Other}]$ and $\sigma(ATR_{Other})$ are the mean ATR and the ATR standard deviation computed among all non-fluorescent assays, respectively. t allows tuning of the threshold to define the occurrence of interference. For the threshold t , values of 0.9, 1.0, 3.0 and 5.0 were explored.

For the NAR-based approach, the background noise binary labels were put into perspective. Any compound for which the following condition holds:

$$positive_{background} / positive_{main} \geq t \quad (2)$$

was labeled as interfering with the assay technology. Here, $positive_{background}$ and $positive_{main}$ represent the number of times each compound yields a positive readout in the background and bioactivity matrices, respectively. Different thresholds (i.e., t equal to 0.03, 0.04, 0.07, or 0.10) for assigning the NAR interference labels were explored.

For the approach based on Fisher’s exact test, the binarized main signal readouts from the blue fluorescence-based assays and the non-fluorescence-based assays were compared. More specifically, a contingency table was computed, putting into perspective the two different assay domains (i.e., blue fluorescence-based assays and non-fluorescence-based assays), and the observed activity counts, i.e., the number of times a compound is recorded as active or inactive. Based on Fisher’s exact test, compounds for which:

$$p\text{-value} \leq t \quad (3)$$

were flagged as assay-interfering compounds, with threshold t equal to 0.35, 0.17, 0.07, or 0.01.

For the public test sets derived from PubChem AID 1696 and AID 720678, the existing binary compound activity labels were used for model testing.

Machine-learning model development

Random forest classifiers

Random forest (RF) models were generated with the `BalanceDRandomForestClassifier` class of the `imbalanced-learn` Python library [22]. The hyperparameters `n_estimators`, `max_depth`, and `min_sample_split` (Table S1) were optimized during 50 iterations of Bayesian hyperparameter search using the `BayesianOptimization` Python library [23] using the training set for model generation and the validation set for performance evaluation.

Neural networks

Multi-layer perceptrons (MLP) for classification were generated with PyTorch (v1.11) [24]. The binary cross-entropy loss was employed for the neural network training, and ReLU was chosen as the activation function. To address the class imbalance in the training set, a weighted oversampling strategy of the minority class was implemented. The hyperparameters, including the number of layers, units per layer, the learning rate, and the dropout ratio (Table S2), were optimized with 50 iterations of hyperparameters optimization run using the Optuna hyperparameters optimization framework [25].

Results

Characterization of the data set employed for the computation of assay interference labels

To compute interference labels, we compiled an extensive bioactivity data set from Bayer AG historical HTS primary screenings database. The compounds in the pool of historical single-dose HTS data comprise 1,441,034 unique structures measured at Bayer AG in a total of 187 different assays, covering a substantial part of the biological target space spanning 114 protein targets. The compounds included in the Bayer AG data set represent 227,258 unique Murcko scaffolds. Ninety-eight percent of the Murcko scaffolds are associated with fewer than 45 compounds and collectively account for 51 % of the data. These numbers indicate the broad chemical space covered by the data set employed in this study.

To further assess the relevance of the Bayer AG data set to drug discovery, we compared the physicochemical properties of the compounds present in this data set with those included in the Approved Drugs subset of DrugBank [26]. As shown in the principal component analysis (PCA) scatter plot reported in Fig. 1, the Bayer AG data set envelops the chemical space of approved drugs and extends beyond it, further indicating the high value and broad coverage of the data set.

Analysis of strategies for assigning assay interference labels

Three metrics for labeling compounds as interfering or not interfering with fluorescence-based assays were explored: the ATR (Eq. (1)), the NAR (Eq. (2)), and p-values derived with Fisher’s exact test (Eq. (3)). These metrics were investigated using four metric thresholds for assigning binary assay interference labels to the individual compounds

Fig. 1. PCA scatter plot with associated loadings of the chemical space covered by the 1,441,052 compounds of the training dataset (in blue) and the 4359 approved drugs (in red) reported in the DrugBank database. The PCA was performed on eight physicochemical properties computed with RDKit: partition coefficient (LogP), molecular weight (MolWT), number of H-bond acceptors (NHA), number of H-bond donors (NHD), number of rotatable bonds (NRot), heavy atoms count (NHeavy), topological polar surface area (TPSA), and number aromatic rings (NAromatic). The percentages of the total variance explained by the plotted eigenvectors are indicated in the axis labels.

Table 1

ATR, NAR, and p-Value Thresholds Applied to Yield the Indicated Percentages of Interference Compounds in the Bayer AG Training set.

% of interference compounds	ATR	NAR	p-value from Fisher's exact test
~2% ¹	5.00	0.10	0.01
~5% ¹	3.00	0.07	0.07
~10% ¹	1.00	0.04	0.17
~20% ¹	0.90	0.03	0.35

¹ The exact percentages of compounds interfering with the assay technology yielded by each threshold are reported in Table S3.

(Table 1). The thresholds were chosen to yield, as closely as possible, 2%, 5%, 10%, and 20% of the compounds labeled as interference compounds. The first three rates are particularly relevant to investigate because compound libraries have been reported to typically contain 2 to 5% of compounds exhibiting autofluorescence in the blue spectrum [4, 27], and approximately 10% of compounds showing frequent hitter behavior [11]. The 20% rate was included to study the impact of class distribution on model performance.

We analyzed the overlap of the sets of molecules labeled as assay

interference compounds (by the statistical approaches, applying the four defined thresholds) to investigate the relationship between the three labeling strategies (Fig. 2). The overlap of the three labeling strategies for assay interference compounds amounted to approximately 43% of the total number of assay interference compounds (at any investigated threshold). The ATR and NAR labeled similar compounds as assay interference compounds. Specifically, 70% of all assay interference compounds were identified by both the ATR and NAR (at the 2% and 5% thresholds, Fig. 2A and B), with NAR assay interference compounds progressively becoming a subset of ATR positives as the number of assay interference compounds increased.

When comparing the compounds identified as interfering with the assay technology, Fisher's exact test showed greater similarity with ATR at the 2% threshold, with about 60% overlapping compounds (Fig. 2). Unlike what was observed for ATR and NAR, for Fisher's exact test, when more interfering compounds are found, differences with other compound labeling strategies arise. Specifically, only 30% of the compounds flagged with Fisher's exact test overlap with those identified by ATR.

As pointed out earlier, the study shows a considerable overlap

Fig. 2. Numbers of molecules labeled as interference compounds based on the ATR, NAR, and p-values derived from Fisher's exact test, computed using thresholds for labeling compounds as frequent hitters of (A) 2%, (B) 5%, (C) 10%, and (D) 20%.

between the ATR and NAR strategies, indicating similarity in the compounds identified as assay interfering. However, differences emerge when comparing Fisher's exact test with ATR and NAR, particularly as the number of yielded interfering compounds increases. This suggests that, while there is some consistency between the labeling strategies, each approach may capture unique subsets of interfering compounds, highlighting the importance of considering multiple strategies for comprehensive analysis.

Characterization of the data sets employed for the development and testing of machine learning models

From the 1,441,034 compounds in the pool of historical single-dose HTS data available at Bayer AG, we selected 1,130,711 unique compounds using a scaffold split strategy to train machine learning models. The compounds included in the Bayer AG training set represent 197,095 unique Murcko scaffolds. Similarly to the observations made for the complete data set, 98 % of the Murcko scaffolds are associated with fewer than 45 compounds and collectively account for 51 % of the training data. These numbers indicate the broad chemical space covered by the data set employed for training the new machine-learning models.

In analogy to the work of Yang et al. [14], a test set was prepared to evaluate the validity of the devised labeling strategies and machine learning models. The test set was derived from two counter-screen data sets for the detection of autofluorescent compounds in the blue emission spectrum ($\lambda \sim 490$ nm), PubChem Bioassay AID1696 and AID720678 (see Methods for details). The processed test set (duplicated structures and compounds overlapping with the training set removed) consists of 10,031 compounds (382 autofluorescent and 9649 non-autofluorescent) based on 2549 unique Murcko scaffolds, of which 266 scaffolds cover the autofluorescent compounds. Ninety-nine percent of the Murcko scaffolds represent fewer than 45 compounds and collectively account for 51 % of the test data, confirming the high molecular diversity of the

test set.

Fig. 3 visually represents the chemical space covered by the PubChem-derived test set using TMAP [28]. The TMAP shows examples of individual autofluorescent compounds embedded in chemical spaces otherwise occupied by non-autofluorescent compounds (panels A and B), and examples of autofluorescent compounds embedded in clusters of autofluorescent compounds (panels C and D). It is expected that the latter represent simpler cases for machine learning classifiers.

To understand the structural relatedness of the compounds included in the Bayer AG training set and the PubChem-derived test set, we calculated the pairwise maximum similarity between the compounds from both data sets based on Tanimoto coefficients based on Morgan fingerprints (Fig. 4). The median of all pairwise maximum similarities is 0.53, with 50 % of the values between 0.42 and 0.63. These numbers indicate that a substantial proportion of the compounds in the test set are structurally distinct from those in the Bayer AG training set.

Development of machine learning classifiers for assay interference prediction

Prior to model building, the Bayer AG dataset was split, based on Murcko scaffolds (Table 2), into three subsets: a training set (80 % of the data), a validation set (10 % of the data), and a test set (10 % of the data). Importantly, the percentage of interference compounds was maintained across the data set splits.

A total of 24 models were generated, resulting from the combination of two machine learning algorithms (i.e., RF and MLP classifiers), three labeling strategies (i.e., ATR, NAR, and Fisher's exact test), and four thresholds for labeling compounds as (non) interfering with fluorescence-based assays (Table 1). The established Morgan fingerprints (radius 2; length 2048 bits) were employed as molecular representations for all models.

Hyperparameter optimization was performed through Bayesian

Fig. 3. TMAP of the PubChem-derived test set chemical space, with experimentally confirmed autofluorescent compounds in red and experimentally confirmed non-autofluorescent compounds in blue. (A) and (B) show examples of individual autofluorescent compounds embedded in chemical spaces otherwise occupied by non-autofluorescent compounds. (C) and (D) show examples of autofluorescent compounds embedded in clusters of autofluorescent compounds. The TMAP was computed using Morgan fingerprints with a radius of 2 and a length of 2048 bits.

Fig. 4. Density plots visualizing the distribution of maximum pairwise similarities (quantified as Tanimoto coefficients calculated on Morgan fingerprints with a radius of 2 and a length of 2048 bits) between the compounds of the Bayer AG training set and (A) the full PubChem-derived test set and (B) the subset of known autofluorescent compounds of the PubChem-derived test set. In each panel, the continuous vertical line indicates the distribution median, while the two dashed vertical lines encompass the interquartile range.

Table 2
Number of Compounds and Murcko Scaffolds Represented in the Training, Validation, and Test Sets Derived from the Bayer AG Dataset.

Bayer AG dataset derived	# of compounds	# of Murcko scaffolds
Training Set¹	1,130,711	197,095
Validation Set¹	135,830	48,559
Test Set¹	174,493	58,932

¹ The numbers of compounds interfering with the assay technology are reported in Table S4, Table S5, and Table S6 for the training, validation, and test set, respectively.

optimization for the RF (optimizing the number of trees, maximum depth of each tree, and bootstrap usage) and through Optuna optimization for the MLP (optimizing the number of neurons per layer, number of layers, dropout rate, and learning rate), using the Bayer AG training

Table 3
Model Performance on the Bayer AG Test Set and the PubChem Bioassay-derived Test Set.

Algorithm	Labeling method	%interference compounds threshold	Bayer AG Test Set ¹				PubChem Bioassay-derived test set					
			MCC ²	AUC	Precision	Recall	MCC ²	AUC	Precision	Recall		
RF	ATR	20 %	0.42	0.87	0.34	0.81	0.35	0.91	0.20	0.75		
		10 %	0.45	0.87	0.40	0.75	0.36	0.91	0.21	0.75		
		5 %	0.38	0.91	0.23	0.81	0.33	0.91	0.18	0.73		
		2 %	0.25	0.94	0.09	0.86	0.31	0.90	0.17	0.73		
		20 %	0.47	0.85	0.47	0.72	0.35	0.91	0.19	0.79		
		10 %	0.44	0.88	0.36	0.77	0.35	0.91	0.19	0.81		
	NAR	5 %	0.41	0.91	0.27	0.80	0.36	0.91	0.21	0.75		
		2 %	0.33	0.94	0.15	0.86	0.35	0.91	0.19	0.78		
		20 %	0.41	0.80	0.49	0.61	0.41	0.93	0.31	0.63		
		10 %	0.41	0.86	0.32	0.73	0.42	0.93	0.29	0.71		
		p-Values derived from Fisher exact test		5 %	0.37	0.89	0.23	0.76	0.45	0.94	0.34	0.66
			2 %	0.29	0.92	0.12	0.80	0.44	0.94	0.32	0.69	
MLP	ATR	20 %	0.38	0.84	0.30	0.80	0.20	0.80	0.10	0.66		
		10 %	0.42	0.84	0.37	0.71	0.21	0.79	0.13	0.57		
		5 %	0.43	0.89	0.42	0.50	0.22	0.82	0.20	0.32		
		2 %	0.32	0.91	0.17	0.70	0.26	0.79	0.22	0.39		
		20 %	0.43	0.82	0.47	0.65	0.22	0.80	0.12	0.63		
		10 %	0.41	0.85	0.34	0.73	0.24	0.82	0.13	0.66		
	NAR	5 %	0.43	0.88	0.34	0.67	0.23	0.83	0.19	0.37		
		2 %	0.41	0.90	0.39	0.47	0.23	0.81	0.25	0.25		
		20 %	0.34	0.76	0.40	0.65	0.17	0.78	0.10	0.66		
		10 %	0.39	0.82	0.36	0.58	0.22	0.78	0.13	0.57		
		p-Values derived from Fisher exact test		5 %	0.36	0.86	0.23	0.71	0.26	0.79	0.20	0.32
			2 %	0.35	0.88	0.31	0.71	0.20	0.85	0.22	0.39	

¹ Performance on the validation set used for hyperparameter optimization is reported in Table S7.

² Boxplot representations comparing the MCC distributions yielded by models trained with different labeling strategies on the test set are reported in Figures S1 and S2.

Characteristic (ROC) curves generated from predictions on the Bayer AG test set. Fig. 5 presents the ROC curves for predictions made by RF in different setups. When employing the 2% (Fig. 5A) and 5% (Fig. 5B) thresholds, the models promptly identify interfering compounds, as shown by the high early enrichment of the curves (slope of the ROC between FPR=0.0 and FPR=0.2). This suggests the models' suitability for hits-deprioritization, allowing the ranking of compounds based on the probability of interference for subsequent triaging. Conversely, a lower enrichment factor is observed with the 10% (Fig. 5C) and 20% (Fig. 5D) labeling thresholds. Nevertheless, as discussed earlier, these models achieve the highest MCCs on the test set.

Performance of the machine learning classifiers on external autofluorescence data

We investigated the validity of the newly devised labeling approaches for *in silico* hits-deprioritization by evaluating the performance of all 24 models on an external autofluorescence dataset sourced from PubChem Bioassay. This dataset was compiled in accordance with the guidelines outlined by Yang et al. [14], and consists of 10,031 unique structures with experimentally derived binary autofluorescence

labels. Most of the compounds in this autofluorescence data set exhibit low to no similarity with the compounds used to train the models (see "Characterization of the data sets employed for the development and testing of machine learning models"), presenting a challenging scenario for our models and simulating a real-world situation.

Consistent with the advantage of RFs over MLPs observed for the Bayer AG validation and test sets, the RFs also performed better on the external test set (Table 3). The differences in the chemical space represented in the training data and this external test set did not lead to a substantial drop in model performance despite the substantial differences in chemical spaces between the external test set and the training set. Noticeably, the NAR-derived models experienced the largest decline in performance. While these models performed well on the Bayer AG test set (average MCC=0.41), they exhibited a substantial decrease in performance on the public test set, yielding an average MCC of 0.35. Similarly, ATR-based models showed a decrease in performance compared to the Bayer AG test set results, achieving an average MCC of 0.34 on the PubChem-derived test set. In contrast, the models trained on data labeled with Fisher's exact test outperformed the rest, achieving a maximum MCC of 0.45. These models not only maintained consistent performance across different datasets but also demonstrated enhanced

Fig. 5. ROC curves obtained for the Bayer AG test set with the RF classifiers trained using different labeling methods and using the (A) 2%, (B) 5%, (C) 10%, and (D) 20% compound labeling thresholds.

accuracy in predicting autofluorescent compounds (using 5 % and 2 % thresholds), underscoring the suitability of various setups for different scenarios.

Unlike the RF models, all MLP models displayed a pronounced decrease in performance. While the average MCC values for ATR, NAR, and Fisher's trained models on the Bayer AG test set were 0.39, 0.42, and 0.39, respectively, the MCC dropped to 0.22, 0.23, and 0.21 on the public test set (Table 3).

To better understand the concordance among different methods for labeling compounds according to their behavior in fluorescence-based assays, we investigated the overlap of predicted interfering compounds among the best-performing models. As shown in Table 3, regardless of the labeling strategy employed, RFs consistently outperformed MLP classifiers. Fig. 6 visually represents the agreement on interfering compounds predicted by the best-performing models, specifically ATR using a 10 % threshold, NAR, and p-values derived from Fisher's exact test, both using the 5 % threshold. The Venn diagram in Fig. 6 highlights a noticeable difference between the labeling methods. Whereas Fisher's exact test and NAR identified a comparable number of molecules as assay interference (919 and 722, respectively), there was only a 27 % overlap between the positive predictions from Fisher's exact test and those from NAR. This observation highlights that different labeling strategies may capture distinct patterns associated with interference. In contrast, ATR identified 1697 molecules as assay interfering, suggesting that the variation in the number of predicted interfering compounds may be attributed to the different thresholds employed (5 % for Fisher's exact test and NAR, 10 % for ATR).

The alignment among model predictions becomes even more evident when examining the TMAPs in Fig. 7. Figs. 7A and 7B highlight the agreement between ATR and NAR models, whereas Fisher's exact test labels fewer compounds as positives. Notably, compared to the ground truth autofluorescence labels (Fig. 3), all models accurately identify regions in the chemical space densely populated by autofluorescent compounds, confirming the validity of our approach.

All models label more compounds as assay interference compounds than the ground truth (382 compounds). This behavior could be attributed to the fact that all the labeling strategies explored in this study are intended to identify interfering compounds (in this example, for fluorescence-based assays only) regardless of the interference mechanism. It should be noted that the additional compounds labeled as interfering by our models have not undergone experimental validation to confirm their interference status.

The public test set reports experimental results only for autofluorescent compounds. Our method correctly recognizes structural clusters highly populated with autofluorescent compounds. More challenging examples (i.e., compounds not associated with any structural

cluster of autofluorescent compounds) are also recognized as autofluorescent by our models (Fig. 7), corroborating the validity of our labeling approach and the applicability of the developed models.

Furthermore, to understand how our models compete with existing tools, we compared the performance of our top-performing and existing models on the PubChem-derived test set. As shown in Table 4, our model outperformed HitDexter 3.0 and ChemFLuo, achieving the highest MCC of 0.45. While our best-performing model achieves a lower recall score than other approaches, its higher precision suggests a strength in accurately identifying interfering compounds. These findings highlight the superior predictive capability of our model, affirming its effectiveness in accurately detecting interfering compounds within the PubChem test set. As highlighted in Table 4, our model achieved a favorable balance between precision and recall (MCC metric). While the high recall achieved by the other models is indicative of their ability to capture as many interference compounds as possible, in a hits-triaging context, prioritizing precision ensures that the identified compounds are truly interfering, minimizing false positives. Hence, while our model may exhibit a lower recall than prior models, the high precision score safeguards against false positives, thereby retaining potentially valuable compounds and enhancing the overall reliability of predictions.

It is important to note that differences in training data contribute to variations in model performance. ChemFLuo utilizes PubChem-derived counter-screen data for autofluorescence detection, while HitDexter 3.0 relies on curated HTS screening datasets for predicting frequent hitters. Consequently, the lower performance associated with the HitDexter 3.0 model is to be expected due to differences in the training task, as HitDexter is agnostic of the assay method and not specialized in predicting the behavior of fluorescence-based assays. Overall, these results further validate our labeling strategy for developing machine-learning models to predict assay interference, demonstrating the effectiveness of utilizing HTS bioactivity data for model training.

Prediction of known aggregators

To further validate our labeling approaches for assay interference compounds, we utilized a set of known aggregators to assess how many of them would be recognized by our models. More specifically, we compared the percentage of predicted interfering compounds between the set of known aggregators and a random subset of 12,643 compounds selected from the ChEMBL database. The bar plots depicted in Fig. 8 illustrate that all RF classifiers predict a higher percentage of assay interference compounds within the set of known aggregators compared to a random compound sample retrieved from the ChEMBL database. As expected, models trained using higher thresholds (20 % and 10 %) performed best in predicting aggregators. When using the ATR and NAR labeling strategies with a 20 % threshold, there is a notable difference in the proportion of compounds predicted as assay interference compounds between the aggregator dataset and the ChEMBL subset. In this case, 11 % and 10.5 % more compounds were predicted as assay interference compounds in the aggregator dataset compared to the ChEMBL subset, using the ATR and NAR labeling strategies, respectively. With Fisher's exact test, the best results were obtained using a 10 % threshold. However, our models are unable to predict the entire set of aggregators as interfering, potentially because they are not specifically tailored for this task.

Conclusions

In this work, we explore strategies for generating predictors of technology-specific assay interference from large screening data sets. More specifically, we studied three statistical methods for assigning assay interference labels (ATR, NAR, and Fisher's exact test) in combination with four thresholds that can be tuned to yield different rates of interfering compounds.

We explored the generation of machine-learning models using the

Fig. 6. Numbers of molecules labeled as interference compounds by the best-performing models derived using the ATR, NAR, and p-values derived from Fisher's exact test as labeling strategies. The threshold applied to the training data is reported in parentheses.

Fig. 7. TMAP of the PubChem-derived test set chemical space colored by predicted interference label using the best performing models: (A) RF trained on data labeled using the ATR strategy with a 10 % threshold, (B) RF trained on data labeled using the NAR strategy with a 5 % threshold, and (C) RF trained on data labeled using Fisher's exact test with a 5 % threshold. (D) TMAP of the Pubchem-derived test set colored by the ground truth labels. Interfering compounds are reported in red, and non-interfering compounds in blue. The TMAPs were computed using Morgan fingerprints with a radius of 2 and a length of 2048 bits.

Table 4
Comparison of Performance Obtained on the Test Set Derived from PubChem Bioassay.

	MCC	AUC	Precision	Recall
HitDexter3.0	0.25	0.84	0.18	0.84
ChemFLuo	0.34	0.92	0.23	0.75
Best RF model of this work	0.45	0.94	0.34	0.66

aforementioned labels to predict technology-specific assay interference. Testing on an external set demonstrated the superior performance of RF models over existing models in predicting fluorescence-based assay prediction, emphasizing the effectiveness of the proposed models in capturing interfering compounds.

The study showcases the utility of leveraging historical HTS data to

address assay-specific interference, enhancing machine-learning model predictions. The developed approach can potentially improve chemical library design and streamline hit-triaging in HTS, offering flexibility in choosing labeling strategies and thresholds tailored to specific screening needs. The proposed framework may also be generalized to other assay technologies, such as bioluminescence, thereby contributing to advancements in machine learning models.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Vincenzo Palmacci: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Steffen Hirte:** Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jorge Enrique Hernández González:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Floriane Montanari:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing

Fig. 8. Bar plots comparing the percentage of predicted interfering compounds between the set of known aggregators and the ChEMBL subset yielded by RF classifiers using (A) ATR, (B) NAR, and (C) Fisher's exact test as labeling strategies. The percentages of predicted interfering compounds yielded by the MLP classifiers are reported in Figure S3.

– review & editing. **Johannes Kirchmair:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Floriane Montanari and Johannes Kirchmair are Editorial Board Members for *Artificial Intelligence in the Life Sciences* and were not involved in the editorial review or the decision to publish this article.

Data availability

The PubChem-derived dataset for testing the performance of the machine-learning models and the source code of the approach presented

in this work are available at <https://github.com/Bayer-Group/PISA-T/>. Due to the proprietary nature of the Bayer AG HTS historical data used in this work, the raw data used for the models' training would remain confidential.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT to improve the readability of the manuscript. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.ailsci.2024.100099](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ailsci.2024.100099).

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